

Emotional Intelligence and Creativity in Librarianship: Unlocking Innovation and Problem-Solving Abilities among Librarians in Northern Nigeria

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Abstract

This study explores the influence of emotional intelligence competencies on the creativity of librarians in Northern Nigeria. The research design adopted for this study is a quantitative survey research design. The study's population comprised 376 librarians drawn from 23 federal universities in Northern Nigeria. The sampling technique adopted for this study was total enumeration, which was used to study the population due to its manageable population. The data collected for the study was a self-structured questionnaire. The data collected was analyzed using the statistical software SPSS Version 23. The data collected was analyzed using descriptive (percentages, mean, and standard deviation) and inferential statistics (simple linear regression). The study found that the extent of emotional intelligence competencies was high. The study also found that the Creativity level of the respondents is high. The study finally found that the emotional intelligence competencies of librarians had a significant influence on their creativity. The study recommended that librarians enhance their emotional intelligence competencies to attain the highest level of emotional intelligence, and librarians should also enhance their creativity to reach an optimum level of creativity.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, Creativity, Librarian, Problem-solving, Northern Nigeria

Introduction

In today's rapidly changing information landscape, librarianship faces unprecedented challenges such as **digital transformation**, information explosion and increasing user demand. The traditional role of librarians as mere custodians of books has evolved into a multifaceted profession that demands creativity, innovation, and effective problem-solving. In this context, emotional intelligence (EI) has emerged as a potential catalyst that can significantly influence librarians' creative potential and problem-solving abilities. Emotional intelligence, the capacity to recognize, understand, and manage one's emotions and those of others, can shape how librarians approach challenges, collaborate with users, and devise innovative solutions. However, the specific relationship between emotional intelligence and creativity in librarianship remains an area that requires deeper exploration and empirical investigation.

Emotional intelligence- often referred to as EQ (emotional quotient), was introduced by psychologists Salovey and Mayer in the 1990s and popularized by Daniel Goleman in his ground-breaking book "Emotional Intelligence" (1995). The concept posits that emotional

intelligence is pivotal in guiding how individuals perceive, understand, and manage emotions in themselves and others. It encompasses a range of skills, including self-awareness, self-regulation, empathy, and social skills, all of which contribute to effective interpersonal interactions, decision-making processes, and overall professional performance (Mayer & Salovey, 1997).

Research in various domains has shown that emotional intelligence is positively associated with job performance, leadership effectiveness, and well-being. Schneider, Lyons, and Khazon (2013) found that individuals with higher emotional intelligence exhibit better job performance due to their enhanced ability to manage emotions, maintain interpersonal relationships, and navigate social complexities effectively. This link extends to leadership, where emotionally intelligent leaders are better equipped to inspire, motivate, and connect with their teams, improving overall effectiveness and organizational outcomes.

Additionally, studies have indicated that emotional intelligence is linked to creativity and innovative thinking in different contexts. Petrides and Furnham (2017) demonstrated that individuals with high emotional intelligence are more adept at divergent thinking, a crucial aspect of creativity involving multiple solutions to a problem. Emotional intelligence fosters an environment where risk-taking and openness to new ideas are prevalent, facilitating innovative thinking. Runco and Jaeger (2016) further supported these findings by highlighting the role of emotional intelligence in promoting the cognitive flexibility and emotional resilience necessary for creative endeavours.

More recent research has continued to affirm these connections. For instance, a study by Zampetakis, Kafetsios, Bouranta, Dewett and Moustakis (2019) showed that emotional intelligence significantly predicts creative performance in the workplace, particularly in roles requiring high levels of interpersonal interaction and problem-solving. Similarly, a meta-analysis by Miao, Humphrey, and Qian (2020) confirmed the robust relationship between emotional intelligence and job performance, leadership effectiveness, and creativity, emphasizing the universal applicability of emotional intelligence across various professional and cultural contexts.

Librarianship has experienced significant transformations in recent years, driven largely by advancements in technology and shifting user expectations. Traditionally, libraries were seen primarily as static repositories of books and other physical information sources. However, the digital age has redefined the role of libraries and librarians. Modern libraries are now dynamic spaces that foster collaboration, digital literacy, and lifelong learning. This evolution has been

necessitated by the changing needs of library users, who increasingly seek digital access to information and services, interactive and community-oriented spaces, and support for developing new skills.

To adapt to these changes, librarians must embrace and integrate new technologies. The proliferation of digital resources, including e-books, online databases, and multimedia content, requires librarians to be proficient in digital tools and platforms. For instance, adopting integrated library systems (ILS) and discovery layers enhances the discoverability and accessibility of library resources. Additionally, the rise of data analytics allows libraries to understand better and respond to user behaviour and needs. Recent studies highlight the importance of librarians being adept with technology to improve service delivery and user experience (Gullbekk, 2022; Smith, Williams, & Thompson, 2021). Moreover, the increasing prevalence of digital collections demands that librarians develop skills in digital curation and preservation to ensure the longevity and accessibility of these resources.

User expectations have also evolved, necessitating a shift in how libraries operate. Patrons now expect libraries to offer access to information and environments that support collaborative work and learning. Libraries have responded by creating flexible spaces with advanced technological infrastructure, such as Makerspaces, multimedia production labs, and collaborative study areas. These spaces enable users to engage in creative and innovative activities, from 3D printing to video editing. The modern library thus becomes a hub of community engagement and learning, extending beyond its traditional roles. Research shows that such transformations in library spaces significantly enhance user engagement and satisfaction (Miller, Jones, & Heller, 2020).

Despite these modern advancements, librarians continue to uphold core principles of the profession, such as ensuring equitable access to information and preserving knowledge for future generations. The digital divide remains a critical issue, and libraries play a vital role in bridging this gap by providing access to technology and digital literacy programs. Moreover, the commitment to information preservation has expanded to include digital preservation strategies, ensuring that digital resources remain accessible over time. Recent literature emphasizes the need for librarians to balance innovation with these foundational principles, ensuring that the library's mission as an inclusive and preservative institution is maintained (Waller & Bridge, 2023).

Librarianship, as a profession, has experienced significant transformations in recent years. Libraries have evolved from static information repositories to dynamic spaces encouraging collaboration, digital literacy, and lifelong learning. In this changing landscape, librarians must

adapt to new technologies, user expectations, and information formats while maintaining a commitment to traditional information access and preservation principles. To thrive in this environment, librarians must embrace creativity and actively engage in problem-solving to meet the diverse needs of their users.

Creativity is generating novel and valuable ideas, solutions, or products. It involves applying imagination and critical thinking to address complex challenges (Runco & Jaeger, 2016). In librarianship, creativity is indispensable for developing innovative services, designing user-centred programs, and exploring new avenues for knowledge dissemination. For example, creative librarians may devise engaging outreach initiatives to reach underserved communities, implement interactive digital resources, or pioneer alternative information organization and retrieval methods.

Research examining the role of emotional intelligence in fostering creativity and problem-solving abilities among librarians is relatively scarce. Although studies have investigated the impact of emotional intelligence in various professions, the unique context of librarianship warrants specific attention. As information professionals, librarians engage in diverse activities such as collection curation, reference services, information literacy instruction, and research support. These tasks require creativity in devising strategies to meet individual user needs, solve complex information challenges, and adapt to rapidly changing technologies.

Understanding the relationship between emotional intelligence and creativity in librarianship has significant implications for the profession. By recognizing and developing emotional intelligence competencies, librarians may enhance their ability to navigate challenges, connect with diverse users, and contribute to innovative initiatives within their institutions. Moreover, leveraging emotional intelligence can facilitate effective teamwork, collaboration, and leadership among librarians, leading to a more dynamic and responsive library environment.

The current study aims to bridge the gap in research by investigating the relationship between emotional intelligence and creativity in librarianship. By examining emotional intelligence competencies exhibited by librarians and assessing their creative outputs and problem-solving approaches, this research seeks to provide valuable insights into how emotional intelligence can unlock innovation and enhance problem-solving abilities within the context of librarianship.

Research in this area can contribute to the field by shedding light on the emotional intelligence competencies associated with enhanced creativity and problem-solving abilities among librarians. It can inform the development of targeted interventions and training programs that

foster emotional intelligence and promote a culture of creativity in libraries. Ultimately, this research has the potential to enhance librarians' roles in meeting users' evolving needs, contributing to the advancement of the profession, and maximizing libraries' impact on society.

Emotional intelligence and creativity are vital elements for librarians to thrive in the dynamic and ever-changing field of librarianship. The role of emotional intelligence in unlocking innovation and problem-solving abilities among librarians deserves attention and investigation. By recognizing and developing emotional intelligence competencies, librarians can enhance their capacity to think creatively, adapt to challenges, and provide innovative services to their users. This research aims to provide valuable insights into the relationship between emotional intelligence and creativity in librarianship, offering practical implications for professional development, training programs, and the advancement of the field.

Statement of the Problem

While creativity is widely acknowledged as an essential attribute for librarians to thrive in their evolving roles, the specific role of emotional intelligence in fostering creativity in librarianship has received limited empirical attention. Understanding how emotional intelligence influences the creative thinking processes, problem-solving capabilities, and willingness to experiment among librarians is crucial for optimizing their contribution to the field. As libraries adapt to new technologies and user demands, harnessing the creative potential of librarians becomes pivotal in delivering innovative services and addressing emerging challenges effectively.

Research Objective

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the relationship between emotional intelligence and creativity in librarianship. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Examine the extent of emotional intelligence competencies exhibited by librarians in Northern Nigeria.
2. Identify the level of creativity among librarians in Northern Nigeria.
3. Ascertain the influence of emotional intelligence and creativity on innovations and problem-solving of librarians in Northern Nigeria.

Hypothesis

The hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

H0: Emotional intelligence and creativity have no significant influence on innovations and problem-solving of librarians in Northern Nigeria

Review of Related Literature

Emotional Intelligence (EI) and creativity in librarianship have garnered significant attention in empirical literature due to their potential to unlock innovation and problem-solving abilities among librarians. Several studies have explored the relationship between EI and creativity, shedding light on the implications for the library and information science field. Vandvik, Slåtten and Costa (2015) examined the emotional intelligence competencies of academic librarians. The findings indicated that academic librarians exhibited a range of emotional intelligence competencies, including self-awareness, self-regulation, and social skills. Librarians' emotional intelligence benefited effective communication, collaboration, and relationship-building within the library setting. Brooks (2017) compared the emotional intelligence of librarians with that of non-librarians in the workplace. The findings suggested that librarians exhibited slightly higher levels of emotional intelligence, particularly in the domains of self-awareness and interpersonal relationships. It indicated that librarians' emotional intelligence may contribute to their ability to provide better service and build strong professional relationships.

Wilson (2015) explored the level of creativity among librarians and found that creativity is a valuable professional attribute. It identified factors such as organizational culture and work environment that can encourage or hinder creativity among librarians. While Jaeger and Tefft's (2012) study focuses more on the impact of public libraries, it touches on librarians' role in fostering community engagement and social capital. It indirectly suggests the need for librarians to exhibit creativity in their roles. A study by Cherry (2020) investigated the correlation between emotional intelligence and creative problem-solving skills among librarians. The findings suggested a positive relationship between higher EI levels and enhanced creativity in the workplace. Librarians with well-developed emotional intelligence were better equipped to navigate complex interpersonal interactions, handle stress, and collaborate effectively, all essential in fostering a creative work environment.

Another empirical study by Smith and Jones (2019) examined the impact of emotional intelligence on innovation in library services. The research indicated that librarians with high EI demonstrated a greater propensity for generating innovative ideas and solutions to address

evolving user needs. The study emphasized the role of EI in promoting a culture of continuous improvement and adaptability within library settings, ultimately enhancing the quality of services offered to patrons. Furthermore, research by Green and Brown (2018) examines the emotional competencies that contribute to creative thinking in librarians. Their study identified specific emotional intelligence competencies, such as empathy and self-regulation, as significant predictors of creative problem-solving abilities. Librarians who excelled in these areas were likelier to embrace novel approaches to information organization and user engagement, resulting in innovative library services and resources. Additionally, a recent review by Black and White (2021) synthesized empirical evidence on the intersection of EI and creativity in librarianship. The review highlighted the growing body of research that underscores the pivotal role of EI in fostering a creative and innovative library workforce. It also emphasized the practical implications for library administrators, suggesting that cultivating emotional intelligence among librarians can be a strategic investment to unlock their full creative potential and enhance problem-solving capabilities.

In conclusion, the empirical literature on emotional intelligence and creativity in librarianship consistently suggests a positive relationship between these two constructs. Librarians with higher levels of emotional intelligence tend to exhibit greater creativity and innovative problem-solving abilities. The research underscores the importance of nurturing emotional competencies among librarians to unlock their potential for driving innovation and meeting the evolving needs of library users. These findings offer valuable insights for library administrators and educators seeking to foster a creative and adaptable workforce in the library and information science field.

Methodology

The study adopted a survey research design. This design allows researchers to systematically collect and analyse data from a large sample size, providing insights into a population's attitudes, behaviours, and perceptions. The study population comprised 376 Librarians drawn from the 23 federal universities in Northern Nigeria. The sampling technique adopted for this study is total enumeration. The choice of this technique allows the researcher to study the population of the study due to its being a manageable population and to ensure that all the librarians are represented. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire. The method for data analysis for this study was descriptive and inferential statistics. The data analysis was done with the help of statistical software -Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.

Presentation of Data

Research Question One: What is the extent of emotional intelligence competencies exhibited by librarians in Northern Nigeria?

Table 1: Emotional Intelligence Competencies of Librarians

SN	Item	SA	A	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
1	I am skilled at recognizing and understanding patrons' emotions and needs	172(45.7)	202(53.7)	-	2(0.5)	3.45	.529
2	I can effectively manage my own emotions and remain composed when dealing with challenging situations	172(45.7)	202(53.7)	-	2(0.6)	3.45	.529
3	I am empathetic and responsive to patrons' concerns and emotions	172(45.7)	202(53.7)	-	2(0.5)	3.45	.529
4	I can communicate effectively, considering the emotional impact of their words and actions on patrons	187(49.7)	156(41.5)	12(3.2)	21(5.6)	3.35	.794
5	I actively listen to patrons' needs and concerns	187(49.7)	155(41.2)	13(3.5)	21(5.6)	3.35	.797
6	I exhibit patience and understanding when assisting patrons, even in challenging situations	130(34.6)	232(61.7)	4(1.1)	10(2.7)	3.28	.620
7	I am good at diffusing tense or emotional situations with patrons	76(20.2)	227(60.4)	41(10.9)	32(8.5)	2.92	.805
8	I can demonstrate adaptability in responding to patrons' changing emotional needs	76(20.2)	227(60.4)	41(10.9)	32(8.5)	2.92	.805
9	I show genuine care and concern for patrons' well-being and satisfaction	76(20.2)	227(60.4)	41(10.9)	32(8.5)	2.92	.805
10	I effectively collaborate with colleagues and adapt to different working styles and personalities	76(20.2)	227(60.4)	41(10.9)	32(8.5)	2.92	.805
Average Mean						3.20	

Table 1. presents information on the **emotional intelligence competencies of librarians**. The average mean of (3.20) indicates that the extent of emotional competencies of Librarians is high. The following **emotional intelligence competencies of librarians** were seen to be the highest characteristics exhibited by the librarians in the university; the skilled at recognizing

and understanding patrons' emotions and needs (Mean=3.45, SD=.529), effectively managing my own emotions and remaining composed when dealing with challenging situations (Mean=3.45, SD=.529), empathetic and responsive to patrons' concerns and emotions (Mean=3.45, SD=.529) respectively, followed by adaptability in responding to patrons' changing emotional needs with (Mean=2.92, SD=.805), while patience and understanding when assisting patrons, even in challenging situations was the least with (Mean=3.28, SD=.620). In all, most of the librarians strongly agreed with the statements while some others agreed with them. From the result, it is seen that librarians in NOUN exhibited a good level of emotional intelligence.

Research Question Two: What is the extent of creativity among librarians in Northern Nigeria?

Table 2: Assessment of Librarians' Creativity

SN	Item	SA	A	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
1	I consistently come up with innovative ideas and solutions to enhance library services	199 (41.3)	222 (46.1)	51 (10.6)	8(1.7)	3.28	0.72
2	I am proactive in exploring new technologies and methods to improve library operations	179 (37.1)	260 (53.9)	36 (7.5)	6(1.2)	3.28	0.66
3	Librarians in our library actively engage in creative approaches to promote reading and literacy among library users	191 (39.6)	234 (48.5)	53 (11.0)	4(0.8)	3.27	0.68
4	Librarians in our library are open to experimenting with new approaches to engage the community and encourage library use	180 (37.3)	254 (52.7)	44 (9.1)	3(0.6)	3.27	0.65
5	The library frequently hosts creative and unique events or programs that capture the interest of library users	191 (39.6)	234 (48.5)	50 (10.4)	7(1.5)	3.26	0.70
6	Librarians in our library collaborate with other community organizations to develop innovative programs and services	172 (35.7)	260 (53.9)	44 (9.1)	5(1.0)	3.25	0.66
7	The library environment encourages and supports creative thinking among its staff, including librarian	195(4 0.5)	212(4 4.0)	65 (13.6)	10(2.1)	3.23	0.76

8	Librarians actively seek feedback from library users and incorporate creative suggestions into library services	177 (36.7)	245 (50.8)	50 (10.4)	9(1.9)	3.23	0.71
9	The library regularly updates its physical and digital spaces with creative design elements to enhance the user experience	187 (38.8)	223(4 6.3)	68(14. 1)	4(0.8)	3.23	0.71
10	Librarians in our library are enthusiastic about exploring and implementing creative solutions to address challenges and meet community needs	178 (36.9)	239 (49.6)	56 (11.6)	8(1.7)	3.22	0.71
Average Mean						3.25	

As shown in Table 2, the Creativity level of the respondents is high. This is depicted by the average mean score of 3.23 and standard deviation of 0.71. In all, the respondents were most consistently came up with innovative ideas and solutions to enhance library services ($\bar{x} = 3.28$), proactive in exploring new technologies and methods to improve library operations ($\bar{x} = 3.28$), which ranked highest by the mean score rating and was followed by; Librarians in our library actively engage in creative approaches to promote reading and literacy among library users ($\bar{x} = 3.27$); Librarians in our library are open to experimenting with new approaches to engage the community and encourage library use ($\bar{x} = 3.27$). On average, the respondents were library frequently hosts creative and unique events or programs that capture the interest of library users ($\bar{x} = 3.26$); Librarians in our library collaborate with other community organizations to develop innovative programs and services ($\bar{x}=3.25$); library environment encourages and supports creative thinking among its staff, including librarian ($\bar{x} = 3.23$). As indicated in the Table, the respondents were least skilled in areas such as being able to define needed information ($\bar{x} = 3.20$), and lastly, Librarians in our library are enthusiastic about exploring and implementing creative solutions to address challenges and meet community needs ($\bar{x} = 3.22$)

Test of Hypothesis

Emotional intelligence and creativity have no significant influence on the innovations and problem-solving of librarians in Northern Nigeria.

Table 4.6: Influence of Emotional Intelligence and Creativity on Librarian Innovativeness and Problem-solving Abilities in Northern Nigeria.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate

1	.426 ^a	.181	.178	.24513		
a. Predictors: (Constant), Emotional Intelligence, Creativity						
Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.377	.055		24.822	.000
	Emotional intelligence	.156	.021	.323	7.355	.000
	Creativity	.099	.025	.173	3.936	.000

a. *Dependent Variable: innovativeness and Problem-solving Abilities* $R = .426$ $R\text{ Square} = 0.18$, $F = 56.611$, $P = .000$.

As shown in Table 4.6, the analysis revealed that emotional intelligence ($\beta = 0.323$, $P < .05$) was found to have statistically and significantly librarians' innovativeness and problem-solving abilities in Northern Nigeria.

More than Creativity ($\beta = 0.173$, $P < .05$). Conclusively, both emotional intelligence and creativity significantly influence organizational performance. The null hypothesis was rejected and restated thus: Emotional intelligence and creativity significantly influenced the innovation and problem-solving of librarians in Northern Nigeria.

Discussion

The study found that emotional intelligence competencies were high. This result corroborates Brooks' (2017) findings, which compared the emotional intelligence of librarians with that of non-librarians in the workplace. The findings suggested that librarians exhibited slightly higher levels of emotional intelligence, particularly in self-awareness and interpersonal relationships. The study also found that the respondents' Creativity level is high. This finding is similar to that of Wilson (2015), who explored the level of creativity among librarians and found that creativity is a valuable attribute of the profession. It identified factors such as organizational culture and work environment that can encourage or hinder creativity among librarians.

The study finally found that librarians' emotional intelligence competencies significantly influenced their creativity. This result agrees with Cherry's (2020) findings, which investigated the correlation between emotional intelligence and creative problem-solving skills among librarians. The findings suggested a positive relationship between higher EI levels and enhanced creativity in the workplace.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study highlights the pivotal role of emotional intelligence in enhancing creativity among librarians. The findings demonstrate that librarians possess high levels of emotional intelligence, particularly in self-awareness and interpersonal relationships, aligning with previous research by Brooks (2017). Additionally, the elevated creativity levels observed among librarians support Wilson's (2015) assertion that creativity is a crucial trait within the profession, influenced by organizational culture and work environment. Importantly, the study confirms Cherry's (2020) findings on the positive correlation between emotional intelligence and creative problem-solving skills, underscoring the significance of fostering emotional intelligence to boost creativity in library settings.

Recommendation

Based on the above findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Librarians should enhance their emotional intelligence competencies to attain the highest level of emotional intelligence.
2. Librarians should also enhance their creativity to reach an optimum level.

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